

Supplementary table 1. Summarization of the main genes identified in the analysis of articles on the improvement of banana to fusarium wilt carried out in the last ten years.

Genes	Functional annotation of genes in articles
Genes related to pathogenesis and other genes related to defense	
7G16510	Pathogenesis-related protein
6G31470	Thaumatococcus-like protein
1G02580	Thaumatococcus-like protein
6G21330	Endocytinase
CUFF.40341.1	Acid endocytinase
CUFF.18858.1	Non-specific lipid transfer protein 2
5G10940	Trypsin inhibitor
11G16380	Phenylalanine ammonia lyase 3 (PAL3)
9G30640	Germin family protein 12
randomG28090	Germin family protein 3
10G01250	Lichenase (endo- (1 → 4) -beta-glucanase)
9G23850	Lignin-forming anionic peroxidase
CUFF.1900	Type 2 protein associated with bon1 (BAP2)
5G08810	Alene synthase 2 (CYP74A2)
SOD	Superoxide dismutase
APX	Ascorbate peroxidase
RbohA, RbohB	Regulators of H ₂ O ₂ accumulation
PR1 , PR2, PR3, PR5, PR10	Pathogenesis
CHS2	Chitin synthase
CaM	Calmodulin-binding protein
PR2	β-1,3-glucanase
PR5	Trauma type
NPR1	Expression of PR 1 protein
AOC	Alene cyclase oxide
12-POR	12-oxophytodienoate reductases
MaPAL1 , MaPAL2 , MaPAL3 e MaPAL4	Phenylalanine ammonia lyase
MaCADs	Cinnamyl alcohol dehydrogenase
C4H	Cinnamic acid 4-hydroxylase
CYP73A	Cytochrome P450
MaCHS1 , MaCHS4 e MaCHS5	Chalcone synthase (CHS)
JZ482674	Glutamate decarboxylase 1
JZ482678	Catalase
JZ482691	Alf5 matt efflux family protein
JZ482714	Ribonuclease 1
JZ482718	Nadp-dependent malic enzyme
JZ482722	Tpa: lipoxygenase3
JZ482733	Sucrose synthase
JZ482736	Catalase
JZ482742	Pathogenesis-related protein 1
JZ482750	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase

JZ482752	Non-symbiotic hemoglobin
JZ482757	Amino Acid
JZ482758	Peroxidase 21
JZ482769	Homocysteine s-methyltransferase 1
JZ482785	Ring finger protein 5
JZ482786	Transmembrane 9 superfamily member, type 4
JZ482791	Glutathione s-transferase gstu6
JZ482796	Pathogen-related protein
JZ482825	Metallothionein-like protein 3
JZ482834	Alcohol dehydrogenase 1
JZ482843	Germin type protein 12-4
JZ482846	Ampet synthase and ligase superfamily protein
JZ482853	Monodehydroascorbate reductase and carbonic anhydrase type nectarine-3
JZ482855	Aquaporin
JZ482856	Isoflavone reductase homolog
JZ482861	PR10 protein
JZ482867	Mitochondrial protein type g00810
JZ482879	Type 25 pectinesterase inhibitor
JZ482903	Ribosomal protein 60 s type L5
JZ482909	Protein from the family of nucleotide-sensitive chloride conductivity regulators
JZ482913	Peroxidase type 47
JZ482915	Disease resistance response protein
JZ482922	Catalase
RPM1	RPM1 disease resistance protein
RIN4	RPM1 interacting protein 4
DREB protein	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein
CL12407.Contig2_BXA-1	Beta-glucanase
Unigene5760_BXA-1	Endoglucanase
Unigene9936_BXA-1	beta-1,3-glucanase (<i>Musa x paradisiaca</i>)
Unigene25655_BXA-1	beta-1,3-glucanase (<i>Musa x paradisiaca</i>)
COI1	Coronatins insensitive protein 1
CERK1	Chitin elicitor signaling
ERG	Elicitor-responsive proteins
PERKs	Extensin-proline-rich receptor kinases
FLS2	Flagellin-sensitive genes2
RPS2	Disease resistance protein
RIN4	Interactive Protein RPM1 4
CNGCs	Closed channels of plant cyclic nucleotides
CaM	Calmodulin
CBL	Calcineurin B-type proteins
WRKY	Regulation of signaling and transcriptional reprogramming
BHLH	Regulation of signaling and transcriptional reprogramming
HBP -1a	Histone promoter-binding protein

NADPH	Oxidase or oxidase respiratory burst
GPXs	Glutathione peroxidases
PDI	Protein disulfide-isomerase
BAG	BAG-like genes: athanogenes associated with BCL-2
DRP	Dinamine-related proteins
AIF	Apoptosis Inducing Factor
Óxido nítrico sintase	Catalyzes arginine to produce nitric oxide
4-cumarato-CoA ligase	Phenylpropanoid metabolism
Polifenol oxidase	Oxidation of phenolic compounds
Ácido cafeico 3-O-metiltransferase (COMT)	Lignin biosynthesis
Extensão	Inhibition of pathogen invasion
Celulose sintase	Callose synthesis
LOC103978702	Similar chitinase 1 (PR-3)
LOC104000237	Momylactone synthase
LOC103978704	Similar chitinase 1 (PR-3)
LOC103989437	GOS9-like protein
LOC103975319	Uncharacterized protein type At1g15400
LOC103969557	Transmembrane protein type 45A
LOC103970573	Typo β -glucosidase 32
LOC103992490	Protein 68 similar to the NAC domain
LOC103977235	Type phenylpropanoylacetyl-CoA synthase
LOC103989972	Type PR-4
LOC103992834	ATPase 13 calcium carrier, plasma membrane type
LOC103988092	Scarecrow-like protein 23
LOC103974823	Type 7 α -carbonic anhydrase
LOC103987744	Cytochrome P450 type CYP72A219
LOC103979138	Cytochrome P450 71A1
LOC104000297	EXS leucine-rich repeat receptor protein kinase
LOC103989489	Miraculin-like
LOC103976880	Probable xyloglucan endotransglucosilase/protein hydrolase 23
LOC103979054	Calcium-binding protein, similar to PBP1
LOC103974727	Probable small nuclear G-ribonucleoprotein
LOC103992023	Finger protein RING-H2 type ATL2
LOC103989914	HEX6 hexose transporter protein
LOC104000052	Putative UDP-glucuronate: xylan- α -glucuronosyltransferase 3
MaPELP-3, MaPELP-1, MaLRX3, MaLRX4, MaELP-1	Extensins
MaAGP23-1, MaAGP20, MaAGP19-1, MaFLA12, MaFLA7, MaAGP7	Arabinogalactan proteins (AGP)
MaAGP16, MaFLA6, MaFLA2-1, MaFLA16, MaFLA8, MaAGP18-2	Arabinogalactan proteins (AGP)
MaAGP26, MaAGP4-2, MaAGP4-1, MaAGP18-1, MaFLA1	Arabinogalactan proteins (AGP)
P-loop (GMGGVGKTT) - 'Goldfinger'	Resistance gene analogs (RGAs)
RNBS-B (CKVLFTRRS) - 'Goldfinger'	Resistance gene analogs (RGAs)
Aminoácidos hidrofóbicos 91 (GLPLALKVL) - 'Goldfinger'	Resistance gene analogs (RGAs)

MNBS9, MNBS6, MNBS10, MNBS11, MNBS12, MNBS13, MNBS14	Resistance gene analogs (RGAs)
MNBS8, MNBS1, MNBS7, MNBS3, MNBS4, MNBS2, MNBS5	Resistance gene analogs (RGAs)
MNBS15, MNBS16, MNBS17	Resistance gene analogs (RGAs)
CUFF.11375	Anthranilated protein N-benzoyltransferase, putative (<i>Ricinus communis</i>)
CUFF.24605	Protein of the cytochrome P450 family (<i>Musa acuminata</i>)
CUFF.26496	Flavonoid 3', 5'-hydroxylase (hybrid cultivar Dendrobium)
CUFF.29055	Flavonoid 3', 5'-hydroxylase (<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>)
CUFF.4245	Dihydroflavonol 4-reductase (<i>Anthurium andrea</i>)
CUFF.16156	Polyketide synthase 4 type III (<i>Musa acuminata</i> AAA Group)
CUFF.21668	Polyketide synthase 2 type III (<i>Musa acuminata</i> AAA Group)
CUFF.12751	Catalytic subunit 12 of cellulose synthase (<i>Zea mays</i>)
CUFF.16474	Precursor to putative periplasmic beta-glucosidase (<i>Ricinus communis</i>)
CUFF.1865	Peroxidase N (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)
CUFF.20440	Cellulose synthase (<i>Betula luminifera</i>)
CUFF.22126	Lacase (<i>Liriodendron tulipifera</i>)
CUFF.25302	Lacase-4 (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)
CUFF.29797	Lacase-4 (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)
CUFF.4241	Caffeic acid O-methyltransferase (<i>Camellia sinensis</i>)
CUFF.5976	Similar to T-phyloplanin (<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>)
CUFF.21873	Precursor snakin-1 (<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>)
CUFF.8570	TPA: precursor of peroxidase 136 class III (<i>Oryza sativa Japonica Group</i>)
CUFF.13852	Glutathione-S-transferase Cla47 (<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>)
I, I-1, I-2,	Breed specific R genes
Ma02_g12980	GDSL esterase / lipase (<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>)
Ma03_g01020	Phenylpropanoylacetyl-CoA synthase (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)
Ma03_g03840	Nepenthesin-2 aspartic proteinase (<i>Nepenthes gracilis</i>)
Ma03_g08140	Pathogenesis-related protein 1 (<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>)
Ma03_g11650	Aspartic protease in guard cell 2 (<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>)
Ma05_g26350	Cytochrome P450
Ma06_g10290	Peroxidase 4 (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)
Ma08_g28490	Acid endocytinase (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)
Ma08_g34150	Pathogenesis-related protein 1 (<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>)
Ma08_g34160	Pathogenesis-related protein 1 (<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>)
Ma08_g34740	Chloroplastic polyphenol oxidase (<i>Malus domestica</i>)
Ma02_g23450	3-ketoacyl-CoA synthase 6 (<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>)
Ma03_g01410	Sphinx C (4) -monooxygenase 2 (<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>)

Ma05_g13280	Putric glucuronosyltransferase (<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>)
Ma05_g17850	Chitinase 6 (<i>Oryza sativa</i> subsp. <i>Japonica</i>)
GSMUA_Achr7G01390_001,	Calcium signaling (CaM)
GSMUA_AchrUn_randomG12510_001	
GSMUA_Achr1G26250_001,	Beta-glucosidase (bglB)
GSMUA_Achr3G29530_001	
GSMUA_Achr2G18040_001	
GSMUA_A9	
GSMUA_Achr10G01840_001,	CoA 4-coumarate ligase (4CL)
GSMUA_Achr5G29600_001,	Cinnamyl alcohol dehydrogenase (CAD)
GSMUA_Achr2G15480_001,	Peroxidases (POD)
GSMUA_Achr2G21710_001	
GSMUA_Achr5G04080_001	
GSMUA_Achr10G12260_001	Peroxidases (POD)
GSMUA_Achr8G15650_001,	
GSMUA_Achr9G25230_001	
GSMUA_Achr8G12910_001	Leucoanthocyanidin dioxygenase (LDOX)
GSMUA_Achr1G01320_001	Chalcone synthase (CHS)
GSMUA_Achr5G13210_001	Cafeoil-CoA O-methyltransferase (CCoAMs)
GSMUA_Achr3G08740_001	
GSMUA_Achr6G18620_001	Protein 1 containing the RING domain (RCHY1)
GSMUA_Achr3G08700_001,	Enzyme E2 H ubiquitin conjugator (UBE2H)
GSMUA_Achr3G16360_001 e	
GSMUA_Achr9G05880_001	Ubiquitin Conjugating Enzyme (UBE2C)
GSMUA_Achr7G17820_001	Ubiquitin conjugating enzyme (UBE2O7A205)
GSMUA_Achr7G08530_001	Ubiquitin protein-protein ligase E3 (SIAH1)
GSMUA_Achr9G28020_001,	
GSMUA_Achr6G29800_001	Ubiquitin conjugate enzyme E2D (UBE2D)
GSMUA_Achr7G21980_001	NBS-LRR domain (RPS2)
GSMUA_Achr1G02750_001	Disease resistance proteins (RPM1)
GSMUA_Achr2G13210_001,	
GSMUA_Achr2G13240_001,	Pathogenesis-related transcription activator (PTI6)
GSMUA_Achr4G23100_001	Encodes chitin-inducing binding protein (CEBiP)
GSMUA_Achr1G07620_001	PR Proteins
GSMUA_Achr3G15550_001	
	90 kDa beta heat shock protein (HSP90)
	Pathogenesis-related transcriptional activator (PTI5)

Starch Biosynthesis

AGPase	Pyrophosphorylase ADP-glucose
GBSS	Granule-binding starch synthase
SBE	Starch branching enzyme
SSS	Soluble starch synthase
SP	Starch phosphorylase
GPA	Glucose-1-phosphate adenyltransferase
RPS2	Banana gene S2 ribosomal protein

Transcription factors

2G20130	Putative WRKY transcription factor 6 (WRKY6)
4G01930	WRKY40
randomG14780	Putative transcription factor ICE1
5G14600	Putative protein related to Myb Myb4
5G01960	Homeotic protein bound-1

CUFF.15326.1	Sigma factor binding protein (SIB) 1
bzip	Transcription factor
MaTGA1 , MaTGA2 , MaTGA3 e MaTGA4 e MaTGA5	TGA transcription factor
MaPR-1B, MaPR-1A , MaPR-1B e MaPR-1C	Transcription factor PR-1
WRKY22	Transcription factor (WRKY22)
WRKY33	Transcription factor WRKY 33
TGA	Transcription factor TGA2
MYC2	Transcription factor MYC2
Ma06_g23500	Probable transcription factor WRKY 23 (<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>)
LOC103991268	Probable transcription factor WRKY 50
LOC103992513	Probable transcription factor WRKY 70
GSMUA_Achr10G01150_001, GSMUA_Achr10G14710_001	Transcription factor 22 (WRKY)
GSMUA_Achr4G16980_001	Transcription factor (MYC2)

Kinases

9G19130	Mitogen-activated protein kinase ANP1
6G07600	STE_MEKK (mkkA)
10G21160	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 2
10G07820	Receptor kinase associated with 1 INSASSITIVE BRASSINOSTEROID (BAK) type 1
2G02850	Putative wall kinase associated receptor (WAK 1)
6G15260	WAK2
4G09850	WAK4
MaMAPK1 GSMUA_Achr6P27100_001 (DHPahang)	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase
MaMAPK2 GSMUA_Achr1P11960_001 (DHPahang)	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase
MaMAPK3 GSMUA_Achr9T00750_001 (DHPahang)	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase
MaMAPK4 GSMUA_Achr4P12170_001 (DHPahang)	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase
MaMAPK5 GSMUA_Achr11P12400_001 (DHPahang)	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase
MaMAPK6 GSMUA_Achr3P03110_001 (DHPahang) DAHPS	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 3-deoxy-D-arabino-heptulosonate-7-phosphate synthase
SK	Quiquimate kinase
EPDPS	5-enolpyruvylshiquimate-3-phosphate synthase
CS	Corizama synthase
MaDAHPS1, MaDAHPS2, MaSK2, MaEPSPS1, MaEPSPS2 e MaEPSPS3	Shiquimate pathway
MaICS, MaICSA	Isochorismate synthase (ICS) pathway
CERK1	Chitin-triggering receptor kinase
BAK1	Receptor kinase 1 associated with insensitivity to brassinosteroid
FLS2	LRR receptor-type serine / threonine protein kinase FLS2
PBS1	Serine / threonine-protein kinase PBS1
BAK1	Receptor associated with BRI1 kinase 1
SERKs	Somatic embryogenesis receptor-like kinases
RLKs	Plant receptor type kinases
MaSERK1 (Musa acuminata cv. Mas)	Banana somatic embryogenesis receptor-like kinase

Quinase-2 (LVLDDIW) 'Goldfinger' (AAAB) CUFF.7118	(SERK) Resistance gene analogs (RGAs) Putative chitinase (<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>)
GSMUA_Achr9G19130_001 GSMUA_Achr1G05040_001, GSMUA_Achr2G17730_001, GSMUA_Achr3G18430_001	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 3 (MEKK3) Calcium-dependent protein kinase (CDPK)
GSMUA_Achr6G18620_001	S-phase kinase-associated protein 2 (SKP2)

Genes related to autophagy

MaATG	Autophagy
ATG5a	Autophagy
ATG5b	Autophagy
ATG8ca	Autophagy
ATG8cb	Autophagy
ATG8fa	Autophagy
ATG8fb	Autophagy
ATG8ga	Autophagy
ATG8gb	Autophagy
ATG9b	Autophagy
ATG8ia	Autophagy
ATG8ib	Autophagy
ATG9a	Autophagy

RNAs

ma- miR169a	MicroRNAs
ma-miR169b	MicroRNAs
LNC_001416	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_001766	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_002310	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_000280	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_002429	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_002859	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_001586	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_000270	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_001024	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_000367	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_000730	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_002605	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_002386	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_001103	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_001394	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_003245	Long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs)
LNC_000623	antisense_lncRNA
LNC_000105	antisense_lncRNA
LNC_001140	antisense_lncRNA
LNC_000456	antisense_lncRNA
LNC_001434	antisense_lncRNA
LNC_001506	antisense_lncRNA

Rboh	respiratory protein oxidase homologous protein A-like mRNA
miR166, miR396, miR159, miR156	MicroRNAs
miR398, miR529, miR444, miR2118, miR394, miR393 e miR5077	MicroRNAs
mac-miR156a.1, mac-miR167.1, macmiR397a.1, mac-miR397a.2,	MicroRNAs
mac-miR845, mac-miR164a.1, mac-miR397a.3, mac-miR397b-3p ,	MicroRNAs
mac-miR397.1, mac-nmiR13, mac-miR397.2, mac-miR160a-3p,	MicroRNAs
mac-miR160d-3p, macmiR164e, mac-miR397b.1, mac-miR397b.2 e mac-miR397.4	MicroRNAs
musa-MIR-seq5, musa-MIR-seq6, musa-MIR-seq7, musa-MIR-seq8, musa-MIR-seq8	MicroRNAs
musa-MIR-156, musa-MIR-157, musa-MIR-159, musa-MIR-160, musa-MIR-162	MicroRNAs
musa-MIR-164, musa-MIR-165, musa-MIR-166, musa-MIR-167, musa-MIR-168	MicroRNAs
musa-MIR-169, musa-MIR-171, musa-MIR-172, musa-MIR-319, musa-MIR-390	MicroRNAs
musa-MIR-393, musa-MIR-394, musa-MIR-395, musa-MIR-396, musa-MIR-399	MicroRNAs
musa-MIR-408, musa-MIR-528, musa-MIR-529, musa-MIR-530, musa-MIR-535	MicroRNAs
musa-MIR-827, musa-MIR-828, musa-MIR-858, musa-MIR-1511, musa-MIR-2916	MicroRNAs

Biossíntese e sinalização de hormônios

JAZ	Protein from the jasmonate domain JAZ 1
No gene expression PR 1 (NPR1)	Regulatory component in SA signaling Pathogenic-inducible salicylic acid glycosyltransferase
SAG	Key enzyme in SA biosynthesis
Phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL)	Key enzyme in SA biosynthesis
Isochorismate synthase (ICS)	Key enzyme in biosynthesis of jasmonic acid (JA)
Lipoxygenase (LOX)	Key enzyme in biosynthesis of jasmonic acid
Alene synthase oxide (AOS)	Signaling NOW
Motif Jasmonate Proteins ZIM (JAZ) (TIFY10B)	Encodes the regulatory protein NPR1
GSMUA_Achr6G00950_001	Encodes the transcription factor TGA
GSMUA_Achr8G05800_001	Domain jasmonato -ZIM (JAZ)
GSMUA_AchrUn_randomG27570_001	Jasmonic acid-amino synthetase (JAR1)
GSMUA_Achr4G08460_001	Protein phosphatase 2C (PP2C)
GSMUA_Achr10G14430_001,	Binding factor to elements responsive to ABA (ABF)
GSMUA_Achr11G21980_001	Serine/threonine-protein kinase (SnRK2)
GSMUA_Achr6G15970_001,	Abscisic acid receptor (PYR / PYL)
GSMUA_Achr6G30550_001	Coding auxin inflow conveyors (LAX)
GSMUA_Achr11G11970_001	Auxin response encoding proteins (IAAs)
GSMUA_Achr10G27940_001	Abscisic acid, stress, induction of ripening
GSMUA_Achr11G24200_001,	1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate oxidase
GSMUA_Achr6G25630_001	
GSMUA_Achr3G16300_001,	
GSMUA_Achr4G21030_001, GSMUA_Achr9G2960	
MpAsr (plantain)	
randomG26960	

randomG20430	1- aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate oxidase
5G09690	1- aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate oxidase
2G07300	Ethylene-responsive transcription factor 1 (ERF1)
4G05520	ERF1B
randomG27100	ERF071
randomG16100	ERF9
11G20930	ERF2
GSMUA_Achr11G02140_001,	Ethylene Receiver (ETR)
GSMUA_Achr8G14350_001	
GSMUA_Achr4G30680_001,	They encode the F-box protein binding to EIN3
GSMUA_Achr4G30680_001	((EBF1_2)
GSMUA_Achr4G30680_001, GSMUA_Achr4G305ij_9	They encode the F-box protein binding to EIN3
	((EBF1_2)
GSMUA_Achr5G19610_001	Encodes ethylene-responsive transcription factor 1
	(ERF1)
JZ482679	Lipoxygenase
